

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B409
Date: 27/10/08
Take Off: 19:58:45
Landing: 00:28:32
Flight Time 4h29m47s

Campaign: VOCALS

Operating Area: POC flight, centred in the Pacific at 21 deg S, 77.5 W

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Luc Lathowers	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Alan Foster	Directflight	
3	CCM1	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist 1	Hugh Coe	Manchester University	
5	Mission Scientist 2	Grant Allan	Manchester University	
6	Mission Scientist 3	Steve Abel	Met Office	
7	Flight Manager	Stephen Devereau	FAAM	
8	Core Chem / Buck / FTP	Kate Turnbull	FAAM	
9	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office	
10	CCN	Jamie Trembath	FAAM	
11	MARSS/DEIMOS	Jeff Norwood-Brown	Met Office	
12	ARIES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office	
13	Wet Neph / PSAP	Dave Tiddeman	Met Office	
14	VACC	Mark Bart	Leeds University	
15	Manchester cloud / AMS	Jonny Crosier	Manchester University	
16	CVI	James Bowles	Met Office	
17				
18				

Flight Track:

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B409
 Date: 27 October 2008
 Project: VOCALS
 Location: South East Pacific off coast of Chile

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
194349		!	0.10 kft	027	start engines
195213		!	0.10 kft	027	start taxi
195327		!	0.10 kft	020	ASPs open
195845		T/O	0.73 kft	243	
200110		!	3.2 kft	247	Nevzorov zero
200232		!	5.7 kft	245	JW zero
211259		!	22.0 kft	256	Heimann cal
212459	214212	Profile 1	22.0 - 5.0 kft	244	
214450	220257	Run 1	4.8 kft	228	
215522		!	4.8 kft	213	Nevzorov/JW zero
220258	220656	Profile 2	4.8 - 0.82 kft	211	
220832	223924	Run 2	0.82 - 0.83 kft	213	
220938		!Nev JW zero	0.78 kft	035	Nevzorov/JW zero
221022		!	0.80 kft	033	Heimann cal
224028	224412	Profile 3	0.89 - 4.6 kft	203	
224509	224607	Profile 4	4.5 - 3.7 kft	205	
224614	230611	Run 3	3.6 - 3.4 kft	205	
224906		!	3.6 kft	209	DLU reset @ 224645
230517		!	3.4 kft	209	Nevzorov/JW zero
230655	231317	Profile 5	3.4 - 10.1 kft	323	
242832		Land	0.02 kft	068	at Arica
243500		!Park posn		18	21.00S 70 20.21W

B409 Track 27-OCT-08

SCAR -> SCDA - Overview

NavData Cycle 2008-10 Expired: Thursday, 23 October 2008.

Scale: 1:2807038 (1 inch = 38.50 naut mi). Printed on 27 Oct 2008

76996;68

FliteStar 9.4.2.0

Sortie Flight B409
27th October 2008.
VOCALS POC Mission 1

Mission Scientists: Hugh Coe, Grant Allen (Uni. Manchester), Steven Abel (Met Office)

Outline Schedule (Local time):

13:00 Power to aircraft – Warm-up
16:00 Briefing
16:15 Clear Aircraft and Security check
16:30 Doors close
17:00 Takeoff from Arica
23:00 Land at Arica
23:30 Debrief on aircraft
16:00 Power Down

Aims:

To measure the dynamics, microphysical and large-scale structure, chemistry and processes of a cluster of closed convective cells (a.k.a. Pockets of Open Cells - POCS) embedded in marine stratocumulus off the West Coast of Chile.

Location:

South East Pacific off the West Coast of Chile (circa 77.5 W, 21.5 S).

Sortie Summary:

After a take-off from Arica, Chile, at 5pm local (20:00 UTC) and a transit at high altitude (FL230) to a region where POCs are observed over the SE Pacific, we will descend to within cloud and fly 30-minute raster runs through POC/cloud boundaries. Runs will consist of below, in, and above cloud runs to sample dynamics and processes within, across, above and below the POC boundary, followed by a high level transit return to Arica.

Weather:

Thin marine stratocumulus expected over the entire transit area with a cloud base of approx 1500 ft and max cloud top of 5000 ft. Light southeasterly winds at low levels, light north-westerlies at high levels (greater than 20000 ft).

Way points

PAPA = 21'30 S, 77'30 W

Note that PAPA should be at the boundary of a POC; if necessary this point can be repositioned

Sortie Detail with approximate timings:

1. Take off and transit to point PAPA (21°30 S, 77°30 W) at high altitude (FL 230) (T+ 1h 40m)
2. Profile Descent to FL 55 (or above cloud) at 1000ft/min and fly a 30-minute run above cloud and into clear air over the POC. (T+ 2h 10m)
3. Descend and turn 180 degrees to FL 10 (or just below cloud) within the POC and fly a 30-minute run from clear air to under cloud at the POC boundary (T+ 2h 40m)
4. Ascend and turn 180 degrees to FL 30 (or to an altitude within cloud) and fly a 30-minute run at cloud level from clear air into cloud at the POC boundary (T + 3h 10m)
5. Turn to Arica recovery radial and descend to minimum safe altitude (1000 ft) and perform a profile ascent at 1000ft/min to FL 100, followed by a climb to FL 230. (T + 3h 30m)
6. High level recovery to Arica (FL 230) (T+5 h)

Key Instrument Details:

SWS –not operated.

AMS – operated, but manned by Manchester cloud rack.

ARIES/MARSS –according to separate instructions.

CVI - During high level transits, operate in aerosol mode with CVI hygrometer operating, during in cloud runs operate in counter-flow mode

Miss Scientist Notes:

Aim is to measure the POC boundary above, within and below the cloud level.

Information:

GOES Image shows visible image at 15:58 UTC (12:58 local), showing POC in the centre of the box. The box defines our area of operations, centred on 21°30 S, 77°30 W with roughly a +/- 2 degree area of ops. Lines show estimated trajectories ending at 0 UTC (9 pm local)

BAE-146 Scientist Mission Summary Report (VOCALS)

Author of report: Hugh Coe

Mission Number: B409

Type of Mission: POCmission

Start of Mission(UTC): 2008/10/27 20:00

End of Mission(UTC): 2008/10/28 00:30

Submitted at(UTC): 2008/10/28 02:53

MISSION REPORT:

Mission Scientist Debrief

26/10/2008

Flight B408

VOCALS

Hugh Coe

Flight 1

Mission profile

Take off from Arica and commence immediate profile ascent on track towards point PAPA (21S 77.5W) at transit speed at 23,000 ft. Overhead at PAPA the cloud edge between the continuous Sc and the POC region could easily be seen. The edge of the POC region was marked by convective cells which extended to around 300 ft above the main Sc around this region. A profile descent was conducted to 500 ft above cloud top heading towards the NE. An SLR perpendicular to the POC edge was followed at 500' above cloud top (4900'), started at 21:44:50UT to 22:02:58 UT.

The edge of the POC region was observed as a sharp transition in the IR camera surface temperature at 21.2S 77.4W. The last half of the run continued above the POC region. The Sc deck to the north was fully developed, however, to the south the cloud was patchy and thin with many clear sky regions. At the southern end of the leg there were several convective turrets, which possibly marked the southern POC boundary. During the course of the run there was a marked decrease in ozone from 40 ppb to 25 ppb which recovered to 40 ppb at the southern end of

the POC region. As the ozone fell the NO_x peaked at 4 ppb and then decreased to 1 ppb.

At the southern end of the run the aircraft descended to 1000 ft below cloud base and turned onto a reciprocal heading. At the south end there were multiple drizzle cells associated with the convective turrets. North of this in the clear sky region the aerosol number concentrations were higher than above the boundary layer (1000 cm⁻³) and the aerosol size distributions peaked at around 70 nm. There was little aerosol mass and activated fractions were low. The POC edge was very sharply defined, north of this the aerosol number concentrations decreased to around 200 cm⁻³, the CCN activated fraction increased to 75% at 0.1% ss and the aerosol were now dominated by accumulation mode aerosols which were composed of sulphate (2-3 ug m⁻³). There were further drizzle cells at the north end of the leg. The aircraft turned onto a reciprocal heading to the SW and conducted a profile ascent through the cloud layer, to 4,800 ft. There was a shallow layer of broken cloud between 2000' and 2500', separated from the main cloud deck which had a base at 3,200' and a cloud top of 4,300'. The peak LWC was around 0.3 gm³. The in cloud run was conducted at 3,800'. At the north end of the run the cloud droplet number concentrations were 140 cc⁻¹ and reduced to around 20 cc⁻¹ in the POC region. The corresponded mean volume diameter increased from around 20 um to 40 um. Increased updraughts were observed across the POC boundary with peak updraught velocities of 2-3 ms⁻¹. This appeared to be associated with enhanced drizzle Sulphate residuals observed to the north of the POC boundary were consistent with the 75% activated fraction and the below cloud sulphate aerosol mass. By this time cloud had filled in the POC region to a large extent though the cloud had a lower top than the surrounding Sc sheet and appeared to show far less convective structure as well as the clear microphysical contrasts as noted above.

The profile out of the region showed dew point depressions of 35-40 C all the way from cloud top to 23000' with some structure evident below 11,000 ft. Visually the POC region showed widespread filling of cloud with little convection and smooth cloud tops.

Science ended at 23:13 UTC.

Instrumentation

CVI had a problem with cloud sampling on T/O but this rectified

on transit to sampling. Wet-Neph some computer and communication problems limiting data recovery in subcloud run
SWS/ARIE ARIES/MARSS good throughout
Core chemistry CO good throughout
NOx good throughout
SO2 no signals above threshold
Ozone, no problems
CCN no problems
VACC good throughout
Cloud microphysics all probes appeared OK except PCASP possible noise on ch 1.
LWC JW and Nevzorov good throughout.
AMS all OK but baseline is a little high, calibration may be compromised.
SMPS all OK

[Image 1](#)

[Image 2](#)

[Image 3](#)

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comments : gstoss at ucar.edu

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. ⁴⁰⁹ ~~408~~ Date 27/10/08 Name HUGH COE Page 1 of 3

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
19:53 UT.					107° 11kts
20:00 UT					T/O
20:05 UT					Observing PAPA at 21:38
					21°S 77.5°W should be recorded location
20:10 UT					Very marked transition in cloud from the coastal sea to a well developed thick sea sheet with well defined boundary parallel to shore.
					Cumulus overhead quite extensive.
20:18 UT		22000'			21° current estimate for PAPA 21:26.
20:01					Some interesting cloud features to the east there are waves in cumulus and below cumulus in cloud showing sig gaps 10 mins ago - now closed sea plate like structures into thin gaps between the covering all region.
21:11					now lost plates less organised but now complete cover
21:25					Shooting descent over PAPA

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. ⁴⁰⁹ ~~408~~ Date 27/10/08 Name HUGH COE Page 2 of 3

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
21:31 UT		16720'			Break Profile to descend to rgt edge
					Scattered white horses
					Merian shows jumps at 21.1°S
21:42:11		5000'			end profile descent
					can be conducted 500' above
22:05	Profile 2				Cloud top 4200ft base 3100ft
22:08:32	Run 2	1000'			Have gone through main POC upper region where there is thin ad iceplate.
					There are some drizzle cells assoc with cu.
22:12					In a nice drizzle cell
22:21		1000'			Now in clear slots
					V low CCN and acc made from SMPS. CN quite high peak is made at 70nm
					< 5 Mm ⁻¹ or neph
					S 20° 57.64' W 77° 30.27'
					210 030.
22:26		1000'			See line in neph; CCN and acc made aerosol past POC edge into main cloud.
					PCASP reports some changes
					can detect away from POC

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. ~~408~~⁴⁰⁹ Date 27/10/08 Name HUGH COE Page 3 of 3

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
22:30					Into some drizzle
					see drop in CN inc in acc mode; inc in act fraction; seeing sulphate when in acc mode when come out of POC.
					reph seeing big peaks when in drizzle
					POC is aligned with wind at the BL.
					Some white caps.
22:39:24	END RUN 2	1000			VACC sample
22:40:28	PROFILE CLIMB 3	1000-4800			Some scattered low cloud at 2000' some evidence of a separated lat base at 3300'
22:45:09	SCALE PROFILE	4800-3900			" 4300 dead cap.
22:46:07	RUN 3	3900			In dead leg.
					Sig lig water 25 miles to right of track
					WC drapping out close to cloud top
23:10					The POC appears to have either advected to NW or has filled in (prob both)

23:13 END OF SCIENCE

The dead filling the POC region is thinner; has lower cloud top and shows in absence of cumuli form shows much more stable less convection.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.409** Date 27/10/08 Name G. ALLEN Page 1 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
19:50		0			Surface conditions: Sunny, Thin cloud (Hazy), Sc inland. High sea-breeze ~10 kts. 20°C → 22°C · DP = 13°C ·
20:00					Take-off. Cap inversion at 900mb (1km). Plenty of moisture structure in topogram on ascent. Adiabatic lapse rate.
20:05					Transit to Papa at 21°S, 77.5°W.
20:25					Profile descent at point-papa. POC clearly observable ahead. MSI report at raised cloud tops at boundary.
21:30					Some O ₃ increase and RH decrease over POC indicating descent.
21:42					End of run, turn for above cloud leg 500ft above cloud. at 4800 ft.
21:55	R1				Breaching POC boundary. Front of O ₃ across POC. Decreases within and increases on exit from open area.

exit from open area.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.409** Date 27/10/08 Name F. ALLEN Page 2 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
22:05	P2↓	5000ft			Entering cloud at descent.
22:10	R2				Drizzle all around aircraft. probably associated with cumulus seen above cloud.
					No sign of verga on horizon.
22:10					Clear air. Passed through drizzle on run.
22:25					52° 57' 04" S ; 77° 30' 27" W 030, 120, 210, 030. = Centre-point of run.
22:26					Entering POC boundary into cloud. Drizzle all around POC edge again.
22:30					AMS reports sulphate increase on POC boundary.
22:32					Passed through drizzle shower. Both cloud physics report the observation is good.
22:40					End of run 2.
22:41	P3↑				Start of profile climb. Went above cloud here. level off at 4800ft.
22:44					End of profile climb.
22:45	P4↓				Descent into cloud.
22:46	R3	3500ft			Start of in-cloud run.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.409** Date **27/12/02** Name **G. ALLEN** Page **3** of **4**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
22.49	R3	3500ft			<p>ANS reported $4.5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3} \text{SO}_2$. Much higher than out-of-cloud, due to enhancement factor.</p> <p>General Chemistry:</p> <p>SO_2 showing nothing throughout - ($\sim 1 \text{ ppbv}$).</p> <p>NO_2 between 1 and 4 ppbv.</p> <p>$\text{O}_3 > 15 \text{ ppbv}$ background on way out. Increasing at low alt and showing a gradient across the POC.</p> <p>$\text{CO} \sim 40 \text{ ppbv}$ throughout, v little structure.</p>
22.53					<p>Significant turbulence in-cloud. $> 2 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ in parts.</p>
22.57					<p>Cloud physics reported larger cloud particles in clouds near the POC boundary.</p>
23.00	R3	3500ft			<p>Didn't manage to locate POC open area on this run. It probably advected NW. Next mission should do runs along the wind vector to avoid this.</p>

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B4091 Date 27.11.08 Name STEVE ABEL Page 1 of 1

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
20:01					Profile from T10. Strong T inversion at 800mb. Moisture structure in vertical unlike
					BLUP: Above 600mb no moisture structure. In transit out quite a lot of high cloud and Sc shown nicely on DFC.
20:25					815 Sc below. Can see some cell like structure in the Sc on DFC.
20:44				74.2W 20.1S	Small more broken region of Sc on port side of aircraft.
20:51				74.6W 20.25S	More Sc has thickened up again.
21:23				77.4W 21.5S	Over the POC/rift type region now
21:24:51	PI↓	START		77.5W 21S	Profile descent to POC region
21:42:12	PI↓	EVO		77.6W 20:35	Turn to do above cloud run starting from overcast Sc region and heading towards
21:44:50	RI	4800'			POC. CN ~ 200cm ⁻³
					Humidity ~ 6°C over Sc.
					Humidity ~ 15°C in open region
					Sc in POC region much thicker than in overcast region
22:02:58	RI				End RI → Just gone over thicker Sc as shown in Humidity

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B409**... Date **27.11.08**... Name **STEVE ABE** Page **2** of **4**.

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
220258	P2↓	5000' → 1800'			LWC ~ 0.3 gm ⁻³
					Nice biangular profile in cloud LWC.
					ZDC showing drizzle sized drops near cloud top.
220656	R2	1000'			Patchy drizzle around us although not intersected any yet.
					CNC ~ 150 cc ⁻¹
221142					ZDC + ZDS seeing drizzle
					Low accumulation mode aerosol in rift region
					Drizzle patches that we've seen possibly associated with small cumulus towers that were seen in run 'above cloud top.
					As we cross into more overcast cloud region accumulation mode aerosol increasing again.
					PCASP concentrations ~ 60 cc ⁻¹ in overcast region and 30 cc ⁻¹ in open region.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B409** Date **27.11.08** Name **STEVE AXEL** Page **3** of **4**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
				77.1W	Drizzle peak
				77.1W	20C showing drizzle. Estimate of shower size ≈ 0.05 degree longitude. Nephelometer spiking when go through drizzle.
223924	R2	END			
224028	P3↑	START			Profile from 1000ft to just above cloud top cloud base ~ 3000 ft cloud top ~ 4300 ft LWC peak near cloud top $\sim 0.3 \text{ gm}^{-3}$
224612	P3↑	END			Descend to 3800ft
224657	R3	START			SLR through cloud at 3800ft LWC $\sim 0.5 \text{ gm}^{-3}$ then drop to 0.25 gm^{-3} Vertical velocity ranging from $\pm 1 \text{ m s}^{-1}$
225130					w of 2 m s^{-1} coincide with LWC peak of 0.5 gm^{-3} Possibly one of these more convective cells in boundary region between overcast Sc and POC?

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B409**.. Date **27.10.08** Name **STEVE ABEL** Page **4** of **4**..

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					w of 2-2.5ms ⁻¹ at base
					Just after crossed into POC
					hit w of 3ms ⁻¹
225850					in and out of cloud top
230310					Poss Popped above cloud top
					Doesn't seem to be any open region - possibly advected out to NW?
230340					small gap below now in POC? cloud top lowered and much thinner.
230611	R3	END.			On ascent looks like POC may have filled in in the last 30-45 minutes or so.
					Looking at COP for R3
					conc ~ 140cc ⁻¹ at start of run and drops off
					to 20cc ⁻¹ in "POC" type region
					MWD increases over same period

from 20µm to 40µm
Exactly same feature on FSSP.

VOCALS BAe-146 Instrument status Report

Date of report(UTC): 2008/10/27 23:55

Author of report: Hugh Coe

Submitted at(UTC): 2008/10/28 03:00

Remaining flight hours: 55

General Comments:

After POC misison flight on 27/10/2008

INSTRUMENTS / SYSTEMS STATUS

 = no report

Meteorology / Navigation

1.	GPS (Patch)	Comment:	
2.	GPS (Cruciform)	Comment:	
3.	Temperature/Pressure	Comment:	
4.	Water Vapor (Hygrometer)	Comment:	
5.	Turbulence Probe	Comment:	
6.	Altitude (RadarAlt)	Comment:	
7.	Doppler Radar	Comment:	
8.	Dropsonde (AVAPS)	Comment:	

Radiation

9.	Broadband Radiometer (BBR)	Comment:	
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10.	Spectral Radiometer (ARIES)	Comment:	
11.	In-flight Microwave Obs System (DEIMOS)	Comment:	
12.	Microwave Radiometer Scanning System (MARSS)	Comment:	
13.	Shortwave Spectrometer (SWS)	Comment:	not operated on flight B409
14.	Spectral Irradiance (SHIM)	Comment:	not operated on flight B409
15.	Heimann Downward-facing Radiometer	Comment:	

Chemistry

16.	Ozone (CAMP 2B)	Comment:	
17.	NO _x	Comment:	
18.	CO (AL5002)	Comment:	
19.	SO ₂ (TECO 43C)	Comment:	
20.	Sample Bottles (WAS)	Comment:	
21.	CH ₄ /CO ₂ (NIR-TDLAS)	Comment:	
22.	PAN (GC)	Comment:	not operated on B409
23.	Volatile Aerosol Composition (VACC)	Comment:	
24.	CH ₄ /N ₂ O (1C-TDLAS)	Comment:	

Cloud Physics and Aerosol

25.	Liquid and Total water probe	Comment:	
26.	LWC (Johnson Williams)	Comment:	
27.	TWC	Comment:	
28.	FFSSP	Comment:	
29.	2D-C	Comment:	
30.	PCASP	Comment:	possible noise in ch 1
31.	Small Ice Detector (SID-2)	Comment:	
32.	Cloud and Precipitation Imager (CIP-15)	Comment:	
33.	Cloud Droplet Probe (CDP)	Comment:	
34.	Condensation Nucleus Counter (CNC)	Comment:	
35.	Cloud Condensation Nuclei Spectrometer (CCNc)	Comment:	
36.	Fluorescence water vapour sensor (FWVS)	Comment:	
37.	Dry Nephelometer	Comment:	
38.	Wet Nephelometer	Comment:	some data recording problems
39.	Black Carbon (PSAP)	Comment:	
40.	Filters	Comment:	
41.	Aerosol Mass Spectrometer (AMS)	Comment:	
42.	Counter-flow virtual Impactor (CVI)	Comment:	

43.	2-D Imaging Probe (SPEC-2D-S-128H)	Comment:	
44.	CAPS	Comment:	
45.	Single Particle Soot Photometer (SP-2)	Comment:	was not optimised
46.	Fine-mode Aerosol Spectrometer (UHSAS)	Comment:	
47.	Scanning Mobility Particle Sizer (SMPS)	Comment:	
48.	Ultrafine particle counter 1 (LP-WUCPC-1)	Comment:	
49.	Ultrafine particle counter 2 (LP-WUCPC-2)	Comment:	

Other

50.	SATCOM C	Comment:	
51.	SATCOM H	Comment:	
52.	Up, Down, Front, Rear Digital Imagery	Comment:	

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comments : gstoss at ucar.edu

Chemistry Log

Date: 27/10/08

Flight: B409

Operator: KT

Preflight KT

CO, O₃, NO_x + SO₂

No. ? or x	Location	Action	Comments
Gases			
1	☒ CO2/Ar	Outlet pressure is between 2 2.5 bar	
2	☒ CO2/Ar	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi	190
3	☒ CO standard	Outlet pressure is between 2 2.5 bar	
4	☒ CO standard	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi, note pressure	~48
5	☒ Nitrogen	Outlet pressure is between 2 2.5 bar	
6	☒ Nitrogen	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi, note pressure	45
Flows			
7	☒ Ozone sample flows	Flow ~ 0.7 LPM on both channels	
8	☒ NOx sample flow	~ 1 LPM	
9	☒ NOx Ozonator flow	~ 0.065 LPM	
10	☒ CO lamp flow	~ 40 ml/min	
11	☒ CO cell pressure	~ 7.5 bar	
12	☒ CO Pressure monochromator	~ 5 bar	
Zeros			
13	☒ Ozone zero	Performed OK (if not approx zero note values)	-0.7
14	☒ NOx zero	Performed OK (if not approx zero note values)	0.07, 0.03, 0.10
15	☒ CO zero	Left for approx 10 min	~ -1.2
15	☒ SO ₂		
Other			
16	☒ Tubing	All inlets / exhausts connected	
17	☒ HORACE data	Check data is being displayed and recorded	
18	☒ CO calibration	If unattended set to auto cal (40 min)	Manual valve bumps used
TDLAS			
19	☒ 230V	230V power breakers on	
20	☒ 28V	Red LED on front panel (ensure LTI breaker on)	
21	☒ Laptop	On and software working	
22	☒ Data	Being saved to correct directories	
Post Flight			
Switch off			
1	☒ CO	Switch off instrument	
2	☒ Ozone	Switch off monitor	
3	☒ NOx	Switch off monitor	
4	☒ Pumps	Switch off all pumps	
5	☒ Breaker	Pop all breakers on rack and SSP	
Gases (note pressures)			
6	☒ CO2/Ar	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi	190
7	☒ CO standard	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi	48
8	☒ Nitrogen	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi	40
If below 20 psi then the cylinder needs changing refilling			
Driers			
9	☒ Small drier	Change if spent	
10	☒ Large drier	Change if spent	
TDLAS			
11	☒ Data transfer	To memory stick	
12	☒ Laptop	Shut down	
13	☒ Switch off instrument	Pull all breakers IF no other instrument on	
Log			
14	☒ Flight Log	Put log in folder (notify Ruth of any issues)	
15	☒ Faults	Fill out separate log for in flight issues put in flight folder	
16	☒ TDLAS data	Send to project spaces on BADC	

Chemistry Log

In flight **B409**

CO calibrations only need carrying out when the lamp temperature changes, if unsure perform a quick cal first.

During each CO calibration check Ozone and NOx flows are similar to those observed pre-flight

Time	Flight level	CO				
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Count (Hz)	Lamp Temp (deg C)	Cell Pressure (Torr)
19:55	Taxi	88.59	340	30096	40.53	7.54
Time	Flight level	CO				
20:16	FL220	Manual valve turns		29700	40.52	7.54
Time	Flight level	CO				
21:03	FL220	Manual valve turns		29800	40.40	7.54
Time	Flight level	CO				
21:42	FL047	Manual valve turns		29900	38.65	7.54
Time	Flight level	CO				
22:19	FL008	Manual valve turns		30000	37.31	7.53
Time	Flight level	CO				
23:23	FL230	Manual valve turns		29800	37.62	7.52
Time	Flight level	CO				
Time	Flight level	CO				

In flight comments	
<p>Cap on at 20:14 off at 21:30 Cap on at 23:21</p>	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 409

Date: 27/10/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 18:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 2
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
21:24:59	3	0.09	85													Start Profile 1 from FL220	
21:25:55	5	0.09														FL210	
21:26:52	8	0.07														FL200	
21:28:02	10	0.07														FL190	
21:28:55	10	0.08														FL180	
21:29:55	3	0.07														FL170	
21:30:54	7	0.08														FL160	
21:31:53	5	0.08														FL150	
21:32:55	7	0.08														FL140	
21:34:06	2	0.06														FL130	
21:35:05	5	0.09														FL120	
21:36:04	10	0.08														FL110	
21:36:58	10	0.08														FL100	
21:37:58	15	0.08														FL090	
21:38:56	20	0.08														FL080	
21:39:55	20	0.08														FL070	
21:40:54	30	0.08														FL060	
21:41:57	30	0.08														FL050	
21:42:18																End of Profile 1	
21:44:50																Start Run 1 @ 4800'	
21:45:00	45	0.08															
21:47:00	50	0.08															
21:49:00	40	0.08															
21:51:00	70	0.08															
21:53:00	70	0.08															
21:55:00	70	0.08															
21:57:00	70	0.08															
21:59:00	80	0.08															
22:01:00	75	0.08	86														
22:03:00																End of Run 1 & Start Profile 2	
22:03:45	30	0.08														FL040	
22:05:53	50	0.09	105													FL020	
22:06:59	70	0.09														End of Profile 2 @ 1000'	
22:08:27																Start Run 2 @ 1000'	
22:09:00	70	0.09															
22:11:00	55	0.09															
22:13:00	60	0.12	106			20	500								1		
22:15:00	35	0.09	107														
22:17:00	25	0.09															
22:19:00	30	0.08															
22:21:00	30	0.09															
22:23:00	35	0.09															
22:25:00	40	0.09															

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.05V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.3V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.5V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 1.5 CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1.5V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.6V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CVI log

10/27/08 5:34:07 PM
10/27/08 8:54:02 PM Preflight mahem
10/27/08 8:55:25 PM Drierite changed. Hygro pipeing re routed.
10/27/08 8:56:07 PM CF PID will not auto tune in AT and PT mode.
10/27/08 8:57:39 PM Pre flight probs, PCASP looks ok on ground but could not get close to zero with CF, down to 20-30 ppcc.
10/27/08 8:58:41 PM During transit same prob, but also at high level with no counterflow mode PCASP still giving ground levels, therefore must be leak to cabin.
10/27/08 8:59:38 PM Tightened rear swageloks off of plenum chamber and PCASP counts down to normal levels 0-10ppcc.
10/27/08 9:02:37 PM none off swagelok seemed loose but one/few must not seat properly.
10/27/08 9:04:19 PM zero done on Hygro 20:48, noise much better 0.2gms m3
10/27/08 9:06:14 PM cf valve closed
10/27/08 9:20:42 PM check hygro zero
10/27/08 9:23:22 PM peak in PCASP when switching Hygro back to sample
10/27/08 9:32:12 PM decent to above cloud run will be in aerosol mode.
10/27/08 9:45:13 PM r1 above cloud 4800ft aerosol mode.
10/27/08 10:01:31 PM cf on for desent cloud transition
10/27/08 10:05:23 PM Hygro has nearly a minute lag!, but good responce to cloud
10/27/08 10:06:09 PM CF mode worked well, leaving on below cloud in decent to check zero below cloud.
10/27/08 10:07:18 PM cf valve closed, aerosol mode
10/27/08 10:08:07 PM clear air below cloud run, drissle reported visually
10/27/08 10:13:09 PM in shower
10/27/08 10:14:43 PM cf heater up to 53C sp dropped to 40C
10/27/08 10:15:05 PM clear of shower
10/27/08 10:32:28 PM entering drizzle shower
10/27/08 10:34:27 PM cf on set up ready for cloud 2min before end of run
10/27/08 10:34:40 PM cf on set up ready for cloud 2min before end of run
10/27/08 10:36:27 PM cf on set up ready for cloud 2min before end of run
10/27/08 10:37:59 PM CVI only at mo, will add AMS & SP2
10/27/08 10:39:47 PM AMS and SP2 switching, dials adjusted.
10/27/08 10:40:46 PM
10/27/08 10:40:54 PM
10/27/08 10:45:43 PM in cloud
10/27/08 10:47:29 PM 3.8 control need for ams and sp2.
10/27/08 11:05:58 PM good zero in cloud gap.
10/27/08 11:07:25 PM out of cloud, end of science
10/27/08 11:08:48 PM AMS & sp2 BACK TO ROSEMOUNT. dials to zero
10/27/08 11:09:30 PM cf valve closed, aerosol mode.
10/27/08 11:11:20 PM cf valve closed, aerosol mode.
10/27/08 11:32:19 PM cf pump off.
10/27/08 11:32:45 PM cf pump off.

ARIES flight log

Flight: B409

page 1 of 1

Date: 27/08/2008

Operator(s): S. Rogers

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
19 39 04	On the ground		CH	C	71	40	ColdHot 1 min script ^{Oops! Still waiting for B408!}
20 00	Take off.						CBS settled on 40% despite setting.
20 01 20	↑		CH	C	71	40	ColdHot 1 min script
20 30 05	↑		CH	C	71	31	ColdHot 1 min script
20 32 15	FL220		NZCH	O	71	29	Nad Zen Long Run 30 sec script 8/8 cloud below; v. thin C above Script stopped - CBS cooling, so cal would be dodgy.
20 54	FL220		NZCH	O	71	22	Nad Zen Long Run 30 sec script
21 25	↓		CH	C	71	23	ColdHot 1 min script
21 41 50	4700ft		CH	C	71	23	ColdHot 1 min script
21 44 48	"	2	CH	C	71	22	ColdHot 1 min script
21 46 04	"	240x1	N	C	71	23	Nadir
21 48 10	"		ZCH	O	71	22	Zenith Long Run 3 min
21 58 08	"	240x1	N	C	71	25	Nadir. 7/8 SCU below thin
22 00	"		ZCH	O	71	26	Zenith Long Run 3 min.
22 03 13	↓		CH	C	71	26	ColdHot 1 min script in cloud.
22 07 30	1000ft		CH	O	71	26	in thin below cloud
22 09	1000ft		ZN	O	71	27	Nad Zen Long Run 30 sec. CBS! Script locked up? restarting.
22 14	1000ft		ZN	O	70	28	Nad Zen Long Run 30 sec
22 39	EoR.				71	28	
22 50 30	3600ft		CH	C	71	27	ColdHot 1 min script in cloud

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	27/10/08	Flight	B409	log pages
Operator(s)	Jeff Norwood-Brown		Campaign	VOCALS		
Departure			Arrival			

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection						•	
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•	
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•	
FERA on	at time						
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	34.8°C	Ch 17	34.0°C	Ch18	28.9°C	
Temperature controller set points		54°C		58°C	-20	40°C	
MARSS CPU on	at time						
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold				
Target heating						•	
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•	
Scanning on (LMD box)	at time						
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual			•

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers							
Turn on Deimos CPU							
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***							
Start Deimos Software	at time						
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold				
Target heating							
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual			
Weather	Cloud		Precip				
	Surface		Pressure				
	Other						

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time			
Brightness temps 'sensible'						•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot		Cold		
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold		
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again	at time					

size	#	CHARGED	FLIGHT/DATE	DISCHARGED
10	2	} 27/10	NOT USED	28/10 NOT USED
1	1			
10	4	} 27/10	B409 (MC) 27/10/09	28/10
1	3			
10	8	} 27/10	NOT USED	NOT USED
1	7			
10	23	} 27/10	B409 27/10/09	28/10
1	21			
10	40	} 27/10	B409 27/10/09	28/10
1	33			
10	69	} 27/10	B409 27/10/09	28/10
1	10			

#	LOCATION	Ton	Toff	AccVol	Run
40,33	V	21:44:50	22:02:58	BLANK	R1
10,69	L	21:44:50	22:02:58	1098	R1
4,3	L	22:08:30	22:26:30	1192	R2
23,21	V	22:26:30	22:39:20	748	R2

Flight:

B409

KEY

Not Fitted

Fitted, Not Operated

Duff Data

Minor Problems

OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nevzorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Fax machine:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H:

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100:

CIP 25:

CPI:

CVI:

SID1:

SID2:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC 3025 (AMS):

INC:

VACC:

CPC 3010A (CVI):

SP2:

UHSAS:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR:

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B409

Date: 27/10/08

Instruments

Radalt – unexpected drop-out. Removed H821 DLU umbilical: reset ok.

CVI -

Neph –PSAP -

SWS – not operated

SHIMS -

AMS / SP2 -

Core Chem -

Cloud physics -

FWVS,

TAFTS,

AVAPS,

ARIES,

MARSS,

DEIMOS

Aircraft

ISDN Emails

Used for XChat

MPDS

Could not make a connection

Satcom-H Calls

Issues

Nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 27/10/8

Flight No: B 409

Pre-Flighter: Eric Hon

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	☒	Hangar	Collect spanners for core chem	
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	☒	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	☒	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	☒	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
5	☒	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
6	☒	Aft CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
7	☒	Fore CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
8	☒	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
9	☒	HORACE	Recording data	
10	☒	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
11	☒	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
12	☒	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
13	☒	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
14	☒	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	☒	Video Laptop	Checked onboard	
16	☒	FWVS	Set up & check on AUTO	
17	☒	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
18	☒	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
19	☒	TWC	Fitted & signals checked	
20	☒	GE	Balance checked then back to DP	
21	☒	GPS (XR5M)	Checked	
22	☒	Satcom C	Checked	
23	☒	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
24	☒	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	In cockpit
25	☐	CNC	Butanol filled	left to operate
26	☐	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	"
27	☐	PSAP	Pre-flight log actions complete	"
28	☐	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	"
<u>External Checks</u>				
29	☒	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	photo taken, pers on camera
30	☒	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	☒	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	☒	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	☒	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	photo taken, pers on camera
34	☒	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	☒	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	☒	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	☒	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	☒	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	☒	All other covers	Removed	
40	☐	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol** } RSH
41	☐	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	} Purvis
42	☐	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				
44	☐	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		Signed
45	☐	ICEX applied		
46	☐	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more
47	☐	Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

B409 Plots vs GIN Latitude

CO vs GIN Latitude

NOx vs GIN Latitude

OZONE vs GIN Latitude

HEIMAN & CORRECTED SURFACE TEMP vs GIN Latitude

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B409:

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics Processing	No cloud physics processing logs are expected for VOCALS flights
SWS	NOT OPERATED ACCORDING TO BRIEF
VACC	Operator does not create a log sheet
2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI	2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI operator does not create a log sheet
AMS log	AMS operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	16 Feb 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

Digital video recordings in avi format:

faam-video-dfc_faam_20081027_r0_b409_200440_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20081027_r0_b409_210440_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20081027_r0_b409_220440_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20081027_r0_b409_230440_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20081027_r0_b409_200431_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20081027_r0_b409_210431_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20081027_r0_b409_220431_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20081027_r0_b409_230431_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20081027_r0_b409_200434_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20081027_r0_b409_210434_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20081027_r0_b409_220434_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20081027_r0_b409_230434_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20081027_r0_b409_200437_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20081027_r0_b409_210437_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20081027_r0_b409_220437_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20081027_r0_b409_230437_1hz.avi

No Digital8 video recordings were made on this flight.